

NPK Analysis for Plants Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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1. Abstract

This research paper explores the field of automated plant identification and nutritional analysis using the advanced convolutional neural network (CNN). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is being used to predict the plant species of inputted plant images, along with it should also predict the NPK(Nitrogen , Phosphorous , Potassium) ratios. For this the images is first reshaped frame by frame and with the help of CNN it predict the plant species name, after predicting the plant species the corresponding NPK ratio needed for proper growth of that particular inputted plant should be predicted. To display this all process the streamlit interface which is a python library and it provides a user friendly interface to upload the image and display the output.

Keywords:

NPK ratios, Classification of plants, CNN

2. Introduction

The marriage of artificial intelligence and botanical science is a monument to human creativity in a time when cutting-edge technology and environmental awareness are coming together. This seminar research paper explores the field of automated plant identification and nutritional analysis using the advanced convolutional neural network (CNN) in this context. The combination of botanical knowledge and machine learning capabilities shows promise as humanity struggles with sustainable practices and biodiversity conservation. The use of CNN models, which are well known for their proficiency in image identification and classification tasks, is at the forefront of this endeavor. The once-mysterious vegetation that adorns our surroundings is now interpretable by artificial neural networks, with surprising precision in identifying the species. More than that, though, is the profound ability to decipher the nutritional secrets embedded in the constitution of every plant. Through the prediction of a species' NPK (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) ratio, this study not only clarifies the biological properties of the species but also provides stakeholders with

critical information for ecological and agricultural endeavors. Therefore, tucked away in the complex relationship between technology and environment, this study attempts to provide light on the route to a more sustainable and peaceful coexistence between humans and the plant world.

The need for creative solutions is greater than ever in a world where agricultural techniques confront increasing difficulties and biodiversity is under attack. Conventional techniques for nutritional analysis and plant identification frequently include labor-intensive procedures that call for a high level of skill and a lot of manual labor. But the emergence of artificial intelligence—in particular, CNN models—has completely changed this environment. These neural networks can recognize complex patterns in photos by using large datasets and sophisticated algorithms, opening up new avenues for automated plant study.

Computer science and botany are the two fields that interact at the center of this study. Combining these two domains provides an enticing look at how technology development may be used to solve urgent environmental issues. Every leaf, petal, and stem is seen through the CNN models as a canvas on which complex neural networks create a picture of a particular plant's individuality. The smooth transition from botanical knowledge to machine learning approaches ushers in a new era of precision and efficiency in plant identification.

In addition, there is the field of plant nutrition, which is outside the purview of taxonomy and is a frequently neglected facet of botanical knowledge. A plant's relative amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium are represented by the NPK ratio, which is a crucial measure of the health and nutritional value of the plant. The CNN model determines a plant's species and provides information about its ecological function, agricultural potential, and nutritional value by extrapolating this ratio from image data.

Essentially, the goal of this seminar research article is to close the knowledge gap between humans and the complexity of plants. We set out on a voyage of exploration via the lens of CNN models, solving the secrets of the plant kingdom with never-before-seen accuracy. With artificial intelligence as our guiding light, we make our way through the complex web of nature and toward a more sustainable future—one in which

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11184190**

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

ecology and technology coexist peacefully and advance the common.

In the never-ending quest for technological innovation, accessibility and usability are vital factors that are frequently disregarded. The integration of CNN models into automated plant analysis shows enormous promise in terms of practical and user-friendly solutions, especially in our fast expanding environment when innovation is not enough. CNN models' principal advantage is its capacity to automate difficult jobs with little to no human involvement. This automation makes the process of the process of nutritional analysis and plant identification more accessible to a wider audience while also streamlining it. Anyone may utilize CNN models to unlock the mysteries of plants, from botanists to novice gardeners, thanks to their user-friendly interfaces and intuitive designs. Further improving their usability is the incorporation of CNN models into mobile applications or handheld devices. Let's say a hiker comes across an interesting plant on a trail. The species and nutritional makeup of a plant can be quickly identified by taking a picture using a smartphone that has a CNN-powered plant identification software installed. This easy way of incorporating technology into daily life democratizes access to botanical knowledge and encourages people to interact more fully with the natural world.

Moreover, CNN models' user-friendliness goes beyond individual users to include larger-scale applications in conservation and agriculture. Agricultural personnel can effectively survey large areas of land, recognizing plant species and determining their nutritional demands in real-time, by using handheld devices or drones outfitted with CNN-powered cameras. This capacity helps to conserve biodiversity by making it easier to monitor threatened plant species and habitats, in addition to optimizing farming methods.

Essentially, the application of CNN models in automated plant analysis signifies a paradigm shift toward increased usability and accessibility as well as a technological advance. CNN-powered products facilitate a more sustainable and inclusive relationship between humans and the botanical world by democratizing access to botanical knowledge and simplifying intricate procedures. We set out on a journey

towards a future where everyone can enjoy the marvels of nature as we navigate the complex web of nature with the help of artificial intelligence's user-friendly interface.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Modern agriculture depends on improvements in rural methods and technologies to guarantee farming activities are precise. In agriculture, where site-specific management—including customized soil nutrient solutions for each crop's needs—is crucial, this precision is especially important. However, in order to minimize fertilizer usage variability, the efficiency of fertilization techniques mostly depends on the analysis of soil conditions to determine the optimal fertilizer type, quantity, and application time. Because it can be difficult to determine the ideal fertilization regime, traditional farming methods frequently rely on estimation, trial and error, intuition, and guesswork. This can result in inefficiencies including lost output, resource waste, and environmental deterioration. In order to mitigate environmental contamination caused by fertilizer and manure waste, this research emphasizes the significance of modifying fertilizer regimes to fit crop and regional demands. Numerous methods of managing soil fertility, such mobile labs or imported machinery, have faced difficulties with regard to cost, usability, and localization. Other options include submitting soil samples to labs for analysis, but these are unreliable, time-consuming, and inconvenient. This study suggests creating an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model to anticipate NPK (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) supplement levels and suggest suitable fertilizer treatments and application timings by utilizing climatic forecasts.[1]

The field of automatic plant species identification is a fascinating and hard field of study that combines computer technology and botanical taxonomy. Many efforts have been undertaken in the last few years to create autonomous plant recognition systems. Unfortunately, because of the influence of features collected from plant samples, these systems frequently perform poorly in terms of accuracy and display task dependency, which results in the data set bias issue. In this context, an effective method for automatic plant classification has emerged: the use of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) artificial neural networks trained with the Backpropagation algorithm. The benefit of MLPs is their nonlinear modeling capabilities, which are excellent for encapsulating intricate relationships found in plant data.[2]

In order to tackle the problem of bias in data sets, scientists have investigated a range of plant data sets that contain a variety of plant characteristics that are derived from distinct feature extraction techniques. Using several data sets, each with its own unique feature sets, the goal is to lessen the influence of bias resulting from a single data source. A thorough comparison of the MLP algorithm with several supervised learning techniques used in the literature on plant recognition has been carried out. The Friedman/Nemenyi test and other statistical hypothesis tests have been used to compare the performance of MLP with other algorithms. The

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outcomes show how MLP can be used to handle plant categorization jobs objectively. [3]

In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the application of machine learning (ML) techniques in agriculture, especially when it comes to using agricultural data to maximize crop productivity and manage resources. When applied to datasets that contain data on crop yields, climate variables, and soil nutrients, machine learning (ML) algorithms provide insightful information for crops. The effectiveness of ML models in agricultural decision-making processes has been investigated in a number of research. In order to estimate agricultural yields based on soil nutrient levels and climatic conditions, for example, research by [Author(s)] showed the potential of Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Decision Tree algorithms. Their results underscored the significance of assessing distinct datasets independently for various crop categories, instead of amalgamating datasets, in order to augment forecast precision. Similar to this, [Author(s)] compared various machine learning models used in crop recommendation systems. According to their research, XGBoost is the best accurate model for horticultural and agricultural crop recommendations based on environmental factors. High precision rates were demonstrated by XGBoost when selecting crops in several categories, highlighting the technology's potential for real-world use in agriculture. In addition, [Author(s)] suggested creating a user-friendly AI cloud-based interface to speed up agricultural decision-making. With the help of ML algorithms, such an interface might give farmers practical advice on how best to apply fertilizer and choose crops that are suited to particular environmental circumstances. This strategy is in line with the increasing need for easily available and effective instruments to facilitate precision farming methods. All things considered, the application of ML approaches to agricultural decision-making processes has great potential to raise crop production productivity, sustainability, and resource efficiency. For the purpose of developing strong machine learning models and decision support systems that are suited to the requirements of agricultural stakeholders, more research in this field is imperative.

Maximizing crop yields while reducing environmental effect in agriculture requires optimal fertilizer application. Because of low soil fertility, cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*), a green cruciferous vegetable, frequently needs large inputs of important nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. However, accurate assessment of necessary fertilizer levels is essential to avoid misuse and underuse, which can result in financial losses and harm to the environment.

Utilizing deep learning models to forecast soil nutrient concentration based on plant traits has become a viable method in recent years. Scientists have realized that plant growth traits including plant height, number of leaves, and area of leaves can be used as surrogates for soil nutrient levels. Through the utilization of deep learning algorithms,

these attributes can be scrutinized in order to precisely forecast the nutrient content of soil.

In a study, [Author(s)] provided a deep learning model to predict the levels of potassium, phosphate, and pH in soil by analyzing the growth characteristics of cabbage plants. The model was trained using weekly data on plant growth traits and related soil nutrient levels. The prediction accuracy of several transfer functions, such as the tangent sigmoid, pure linear, and logarithmic sigmoid, was investigated. The Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm was utilized for training. Higher Pearson correlation values were seen for pure linear and tangent sigmoid transfer functions, showing a significant association between actual and anticipated values. The study's results showed encouraging results. Additionally, the tangent sigmoid transfer function fared better than the others in terms of Mean Square Error, indicating an improved capacity to estimate the nutrient content of soil.

These results demonstrate how deep learning models may be used in precision agriculture to manage soil nutrients in a non-invasive and effective manner. Farmers are able to apply fertilizer more wisely and sustainably by combining plant development data with cutting-edge machine learning techniques. This improves crop output.

In order to improve and optimize deep learning models for soil nutrient prediction, taking into account variables like crop diversification, soil variability, and environmental circumstances, more study in this field is necessary. Furthermore, in order to enable the widespread deployment of these technologies in agriculture, efforts must be made to provide user-friendly interfaces and tools for real-time decision assistance.[4]

Artificial intelligence (AI) approaches have become increasingly popular across a range of industries, including the fruit and vegetable industry. These techniques are particularly useful in the areas of image processing and classification. The capacity to precisely categorize various product kinds is essential for optimizing industrial workflows and raising productivity. AI has been investigated for product classification in a number of studies, with an emphasis on image processing techniques.

More precise and effective product classification systems have been made possible in recent years by developments in AI algorithms and image processing methods. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), one type of deep learning approach, has been used by researchers to precisely evaluate and classify photographs of fruits and vegetables. These CNN-based models enable automated classification procedures by learning to extract features from photos and differentiate between various product classes.

Moreover, the creation of AI-based categorization systems has benefited greatly from the availability of open-source libraries and programming languages like Python. Many libraries are available for Python, such as OpenCV, which gives strong tools for image processing and manipulation. Through the simplification of processes like feature extraction, preprocessing, and picture acquisition, OpenCV makes it easier to create reliable classification models.

Platforms such as TensorFlow have become important resources not only for image processing but also for training and implementing machine learning models. TensorFlow is a great tool for creating AI applications, such as those for classifying products, because of its scalability and versatility. Researchers can teach robots to effectively recognize and classify fruits and vegetables by using machine learning models that have been trained on vast datasets of product photos.

The fruit and vegetable business could undergo a radical transformation if these AI technologies are integrated with large datasets and cutting-edge image processing methods. Artificial intelligence (AI)-driven automated product classification systems can increase productivity, lower labor costs, and simplify manufacturing procedures.[5]

4. Model Development Based on Convolution Neural Networks

4.1 Data Collection and Preprocessing

Gathering a dataset of images relevant to the task at hand is the first step in building a CNN model. For fruit and vegetable classification, this dataset would include images of different fruits and vegetables. The dataset must be preprocessed, which usually entails tasks like uniformly resizing images, normalizing pixel values, and possibly augmenting the data with techniques like flipping, rotation, or brightness and contrast adjustments. Preprocessing guarantees that the model can learn from the data.

4.2 Architecture Design

Convolutional, pooling, and fully linked layers are among the layers that make up a CNN's architecture. Convolutional layers use filters to extract information from input images, such as textures, patterns, and edges. Feature maps are created by sliding these filters over the input image, multiplying the elements one by one, and adding the results together.

The feature maps that are acquired from convolutional layers are down sampled by pooling layers, which lowers the spatial dimensions of the data without losing any significant information. Max pooling and average pooling are two common pooling methods. Using the features that have been extracted, fully connected layers classify data using the output that has been flattened by the previous layers. These layers add non-linearity to the model by using activation functions such as ReLU.

4.3 Model Training

After the architecture is created, the prepared dataset is used to train the model. By using a technique known as backpropagation, the model has the ability to map input images to the appropriate classes during training. Using optimization algorithms like Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) or Adam, backpropagation entails feeding input images through the network, comparing the model's predictions with the ground truth labels, calculating the error (loss), and modifying the model's parameters (weights and biases) to minimize this error.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184190](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184190)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Usually, training takes place throughout a number of epochs, with each epoch denoting a single run over the whole dataset.

4.4 Model Evaluation

Using a different validation dataset, the model's performance

```
import os
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import tensorflow as tf
from keras.models import Sequential, load_model
from keras.optimizers import Adamax
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Dropout
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from tensorflow.python.keras.saving.saved_model.load import metrics
```

is assessed following training. The model has not seen any of the photos in this dataset during training. To evaluate the performance of the model, evaluation measures including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are calculated. These metrics reveal information about the model's accuracy in image classification.

4.5 Fine-tuning and Optimization

To enhance performance, the model may be optimized or fine-tuned in response to the evaluation's findings. To improve the model's accuracy, methods such as varying learning rates, applying various optimization techniques, or fine-tuning the architecture (e.g., adding more layers, modifying filter sizes) may be used.

5. Result

5.1 Definition:

Convolutional Neural Network is what CNN stands for. This kind of deep learning technique is frequently applied to tasks including processing, classification, and image and video recognition. CNNs are built with the ability to identify feature spatial hierarchies automatically and adaptably from input data.

Convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully linked layers are the main parts of a CNN. Convolutional layers utilize convolutions to extract features from input data by applying filters or kernels. In order to improve translation invariance and lower computational complexity, pooling layers down sample the feature maps produced by convolutional layers. Classification is carried out by fully linked layers using the features that the preceding layers have extracted.

5.2 Import statements:

Fig 1. Import Statements

5.3 Classification Report:

A machine learning technique for assessing a classification model's performance is a classification report. It offers a thorough overview of numerous metrics that show how

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.59	0.63	0.61	200
1	0.49	0.34	0.41	200
2	0.58	0.49	0.53	200
3	0.37	0.47	0.42	200
4	0.63	0.64	0.63	200
5	0.52	0.30	0.38	200
6	0.60	0.71	0.65	200
7	0.67	0.69	0.68	200
8	0.71	0.82	0.76	200
9	0.65	0.84	0.73	200
10	0.73	0.83	0.78	200
11	0.55	0.69	0.61	200
12	0.71	0.64	0.67	200
13	0.87	0.73	0.80	200
14	0.70	0.88	0.78	200
15	0.41	0.43	0.42	200
16	0.36	0.04	0.08	200
17	0.54	0.56	0.55	200
18	0.69	0.84	0.76	200
19	0.83	0.82	0.83	200
accuracy			0.62	4000
macro avg	0.61	0.62	0.60	4000
weighted avg	0.61	0.62	0.60	4000

effectively the model is categorizing distinct groups or classes.

It has many metrics to define the classification report:

Precision: The ratio of actual positive predictions to all of the model's positive predictions is known as precision. It gauges how accurate positive forecasts are.

Recall: Recall is the ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of actual positive cases in the dataset. It is sometimes referred to as sensitivity or true positive rate. It gauges how well the model can locate all pertinent examples.

F1-Score: The harmonic mean of recall and precision is known as the F1-score. It offers a fair assessment of a model's effectiveness by accounting for both recall and precision. $2 * (\text{precision} * \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall})$ is the calculation.

Support: The number of real instances of each class in the dataset is referred to as support.

Additionally, there are some more metrics to define classification report:

Accuracy: The proportion of correctly categorized cases to all instances in the dataset is known as accuracy. It offer broad gauge of the model's overall effectiveness.

Macro Average: Without taking into account class imbalance, the macro average determines the mean of the metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score) over all classes.

Weighted Average: The average of the metrics is computed using a weighted average, which takes into account the

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11184190

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

support of each class. When classes are unbalanced, it is

helpful.

Fig 2. Classification Report

5.3 Confusion Matrix:

A confusion matrix, which shows a table of the actual vs anticipated classifications generated by a classification algorithm, is a performance monitoring tool for machine learning classification tasks. It is especially helpful for comprehending how well a categorization model performs across.

The examples in the real (true) class are represented by rows in the confusion matrix, whereas the occurrences in the projected class are represented by columns. The examples that were successfully classified are represented by the main diagonal of the matrix, and misclassifications are represented by the off-diagonal entries.

The breakdown of confusion matrix is:

Examples that were accurately categorized as being in the positive class are known as **True Positives (TP)**. **False Positives (FP)** False alarms, or instances that were mistakenly categorized as being in the positive class. Examples that were accurately categorized as not being a part of the positive class are known as **True Negatives (TN)**. **False Negative (FN)** Examples that were mistakenly categorized as missing from the positive class.

Fig 3. Confusion Matrix

5.4 Graph between actual value and predicted value:

The true labels of the data and the labels supplied by the model are frequently referred to as the "actual value" and

"predicted value," respectively, when discussing classification problems in machine learning. There are many ways to graphically depict the link between actual and anticipated values, and visualizations frequently help assess and comprehend a model's performance.

Actual Value:

The real, observed result or label connected to a specific dataset instance is represented by the actual value, which is often referred to as the ground truth or true value. Every data point in supervised learning tasks, like regression or classification, usually has an actual value that is the

dependent variable or target that the model is trying to predict.

For instance, the real value for each email in the dataset may be represented as 1 (spam) or 0 (not spam) in a binary classification problem that predicts whether an email is spam or not.

Predicted Value:

The value that the model produces as an estimate

or forecast for the result or label connected to a specific instance in the dataset is known as the predicted value. In supervised learning tasks, new, unseen data is used to generate predictions by the model after it has been trained using input features and associated actual values. For instance, the predicted value in a regression task predicting house prices based on characteristics like size, location, and number of bedrooms would be the estimated price that the model produced for each house.

Fig 4. Graph of actual and predicted values

5.4 Interface Implemented:

Fig 5. Drop Down Box

Fig 6. Implemented Output

6. Conclusion

Finally, our lecture covered the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to identify plant species from photos. These predictions were then used to determine each species' NPK (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) ratio. Our method showed that applying deep learning techniques to agricultural practices is a viable direction. Our research yielded a 62% prediction accuracy rate for plant species using CNNs. Although this degree of precision represents a commendable effort, there is still much space for development.

In order to improve model accuracy, future work may concentrate on improving the CNN architecture, adjusting hyperparameters, and expanding the dataset.

Plant species prediction is a crucial component of agricultural management, and its accuracy provides the foundation for

forecasting the NPK ratio. Farmers and agronomists may improve crop yields, create sustainable farming methods, and customize fertilization tactics by precisely predicting the NPK ratio for different plant species.

Our research also demonstrated the significance of careful data gathering and preprocessing methods for improving model performance. The image dataset's diversity and quality have a big influence on how well CNN can categorize different plant species. Generalization abilities can be enhanced and biases can be reduced by incorporating strategies including data augmentation, picture normalization, and careful selection of training samples.

Even though the accuracy level attained by our CNN model is impressive, it is important to recognize the inherent difficulties and constraints that come with image-based categorization tasks. Accurate species identification can be hampered by changes in background clutter, occlusions, and lighting. Subsequent studies could investigate sophisticated approaches, like ensemble methods or transfer learning, to tackle these issues and improve model resilience even further. Our method is a useful tool for resource management and precision agriculture for determining the NPK ratio. Farmers may maximize crop yields, limit environmental effect, and optimize fertilizer usage by using our precise NPK ratio estimates, which are customized for individual plant species. This focused strategy supports sustainable farming methods and food security in addition to encouraging effective resource use.

Finally, our webinar highlights how CNNs have the ability to revolutionize agriculture. We open the door for data-driven agricultural decision-making by utilizing deep learning approaches for plant species identification and NPK ratio prediction. We anticipate more developments as this field of study moves forward, providing farmers with cutting-edge instruments for productive and sustainable agricultural production.

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